

Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action

#8.4

Citizen Social Science Open Training Materials for social scientists PhD programmes

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List of Abbreviations

CoRe Co-Researcher

CSO Civil society organisation

CSS Citizen Social Science

EC European Commission

UB Universitat de Barcelona

1. Executive Summary

The CoAct (Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action) project proposes to face social global issues by placing citizens in a vulnerable situation at the centre of the research. This approach represents a new understanding of Citizen Social Science (CSS), as participatory research co-designed with citizen groups sharing a social concern.

Along these lines, there exists an important need to provide spaces for academic researchers not only to increase their knowledge and their skills but also to learn about new methods to develop a citizen science that enhances social dimension. Covid situation has obliged to run the school in an online format. The online format has motivated the choice to organise a rather long school (two weeks duration, 9 school days) and to have a daily concentrated routine scheduled during the afternoon. Considering positive aspects related to the COVID situation, the online format has allowed to have a wider diversity of participants and a larger number of participants (39) that were initially anticipated. Participants were coming from 20 different countries. Despite their own difficulties with internet access, we also had participants from Africa and South America. Broadly, 25% of the applicants are MSc students while 50% are pursuing their PhD (66% of early career researchers). Research areas of participants include public health, sociology, biomedicine, political sciences, architecture, law... In addition, following the experimental spirit of any research project, it has also been the intention of the school to provide the broadest perspective possible with 38 lecturers, including a wide variety of disciplines and perspectives, and with the participation of other H2020 projects and the Project Officer of CoAct.

The Deliverable 8.4 is mostly focussed on the delivery of the open materials which are briefly described in Section 2. These have taken a digital format (pdfs and videos) and they are accessible through CoAct website. Section 3 fully reproduces the key document of the school: the School Guide. The guide is a quite extensive pdf document which includes the general information of the school, the detailed contents of each session with a list of resources and the bio of the lecturers. Section 4 includes some final remarks about the whole process of preparing the materials and about the school itself.

2. Brief description of the materials

Due to COVID pandemics, we opted to run the school in an online format. For this reason, we decided to:

- 1) compile an extended and accurate **school guide** where school participants have been able to find out the full description of each session with an abstract, a description of the methodologies used and a list of resources. A bio from each lecturer has also been added. The school guide is available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5789719>
- 2) share the presentations and the video recordings through the CoAct website at: <https://coactproject.eu/open-materials-citizen-social-science-school/>

The school guide which is the cornerstone of the training materials is fully transcribed in the coming section of this report. The school guide compiled all contributions provided by the lecturers and the school organisers in a structured manner. Figure 1 shows some features related to school participants and lecturers.

 The CoAct project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 873048

Figure 1: Basic figures of the school, in relation to the number of attendants, the percentage of early-stage researchers, the number of lecturers and the time distribution.

3. School guide

3.1 Presentation

Welcome to the Citizen Social Science school! A common space to reflect, discuss, learn, and receive practical guidelines to explore social dimensions behind Citizen Science practices.

The school wants to consider a wide collection of approaches and participatory settings inside and outside academics, from several parts of the world.

Citizen Social Science is here understood as a participatory research approach co-designed and directly driven by citizen groups sharing a social concern. There are many ways to enhance the social dimensions of Citizen Science and there are several approaches to formulate Citizen Social Science, but the school would like to emphasize the possibilities of running participatory research involving groups in a vulnerable situation that act as Co-Researchers. Other perspectives will also be included to further complete this ambitious research agenda and thus open a transdisciplinary debate with more than 25 lecturers from a wide variety of backgrounds.

The school takes inspiration from the EU H2020 SwafS **CoAct** (Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action) project's experiences and partners. It aims to invigorate the academic community around a wide set of Citizen Social Science practices while providing a critical view on their strengths and challenges.

The participant will have the opportunity to learn aspects related to the following elements:

- Review of transdisciplinary aspects to Citizen Social Science (Open Science, Ethical Research, Digital participation, Evaluation and Policy Impact)
- Practical examples of Citizen Social Science practices where groups in a vulnerable situation are acting as Co-Researchers

- Portfolio of collaborative participatory research models (interdisciplinary, intersectoral and international)
- Practical tools to maximize success and minimize challenges of Citizen Social Science
- Development of an international network of peers
- Strategies to be inclusive in a Citizen Science project

School participants have a wide diversity of profiles, perspectives, and scientific backgrounds. Participants are coming from 20 different countries. Broadly, 25% of the applicants are MSc students, 50% are pursuing their PhD, and the remaining applicants are PhD or senior researchers. Research areas of participants include public health, sociology, biomedicine, political sciences, architecture, law... We believe that you will benefit from the transdisciplinary spirit in the mutual learning environment that we promote.

Remember that the Citizen Social Science School is a formal education activity officially recognized by the Universitat de Barcelona. You can find the instructions to get your certificate in the practical information section of this guide.

The school is about to start, and it is a great honour to have you on board! Be ready to discuss challenges and difficulties with international experts!

Josep Perelló and Nieves Lorenzo-Gotor
School organisers

3.2 About CoAct

CoAct (Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action) is proposing an understanding of Citizen Social Science, as participatory research co-designed and directly driven by citizens and citizen groups sharing a social concern (See Figure 1). CoAct proposes to face four “wicked” social global issues by engaging citizens in a vulnerable situation. The joint effort will result in the implementation of new or improved science-related

policies and in the advancement of the Citizen Social Science approach with regards to its applicability in concrete fields or research.

Figure 2: Citizen Social Science in Action, with citizen groups, a specific concern, and with the support of the Knowledge Coalition.

In all CoAct Research and Innovations Actions (Mental Health Care, Youth Employment and Environmental Justice), citizens in a vulnerable situation are placed at the centre of the research and their role and dedication conceptually recognize them as Co-Researchers (CoRes). In parallel, the Knowledge Coalition is a network of stakeholders who are informed about the R&I Actions' goals, and plays an active role, either participating in or co-designing different actions, to harness CoRes' efforts and implement policies and measures based on scientific evidence.

CoAct is also developing a general framework for Citizen Social Science, that is incubated in our Consortium made of Research Organizations, NGOs and global networks of Open Science and Open Data activism. Expertise from Computational Social Science, Participatory Action Research or Citizen Science evaluation are being incorporated to conceive a transdisciplinary Citizen Social Science placing citizens in a vulnerable situation at the centre of Research and Innovation cycles.

Sessions Related to CoAct

CoAct started on 1st of January 2020. This school incorporates different outcomes and learnings from CoAct. In several sessions, some of the CoAct partners are explaining and showcasing the work done during the first 20 months of the project.

The sessions related to CoAct are, by chronological order (Central European Time, CET):

Day 1 - Monday, September 13th, 2021. 14.00-16:00h S0: Citizen Social Science: Enhancing social dimensions in Citizen Science. CoAct partners from **Universitat de Barcelona** and **FachHochSchule Potsdam** will introduce the general concept of CoAct and share some work regarding the general framework being developed.

Day 2 – Tuesday, September 14th, 2021. 13.30-15.30h. W1: CoAct for Mental Health: sharing first-hand experiences and co-creating a chatbot for a Citizen Social Science research. In this hands-on workshop, CoAct partner **Universitat de Barcelona** will guide participants to test digital and non-digital tools for research co-creation.

Day 3 – Wednesday, September 15th, 2021. 13.30-15.30h. W2: Digital Participation in vulnerable contexts during Covid times. During this workshop, CoAct partner **Universidad Nacional de San Martín** will share their share strategies to cope with the different challenges in Covid times.

Day 4 – Thursday, September 16th, 2021. 13.30-15.30h. W3: Methods development for participatory social research with young people. CoAct partner **Universität Wien** will open a discussion concerning research methods that can be used in participatory action research with young people.

Day 8 – Wednesday, September 22nd, 2021.

W7: Participatory Evaluation in Citizen Social Science. In this session, CoAct partners **Centre for Social Innovation** will explore some approaches to participatory evaluation that involve participants in Citizen Science activities.

Finally, CoAct is not the only project exploring social dimensions in Citizen Science. For this reason, we have invited other sister projects to elevate the discussion in a broader level. We must thank the participation of these projects into the CoAct CSS School:

Day 9 – Thursday, September 23rd, 2021. 13.30-15.30h. S5: Putting Citizen Social Science experiences together: YouCount, COESO, SoCis, ActEarly and CoAct

3.3 General Information

THE SCHOOL IS FREE: The school is funded with public money, and we therefore considered that the absence of a registration fee should be a must. However, we ask you to make a strong compromise with the school by attending most of the sessions and by contributing actively to the debate that the school is intended to trigger. Be aware that some people have not been able to participate, and some are on the waiting list as the school is full. In case you cannot attend, please let us know as soon as possible so that another person can take advantage of this opportunity.

THE SCHOOL IS ONLINE: Covid is still with us and that's why we decided to move the school to an online format using Zoom. Unfortunately, this means that you will not be able to visit our beautiful city, Barcelona, in a pleasant time of the year, but it also prevents last minute cancellations. Another positive aspect of the online format is that it promotes diversity and inclusion. As organisers, we will do our best to enhance interaction and to shorten the geographic distance among all of us.

SELECTION PROCESS: Only selected applicants will be able to enrol in the school. We accepted more applications than initially expected but kept a limited number of participants to ensure small groups' dynamics during workshops and mentoring sessions. The selection process has been based on the motivation letters of the applicants and it has prioritized diversity of students' profiles.

OPEN MATERIALS: All presentations and contents of the school will be open under a Creative Commons license: Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International (**CC BY-SA 4.0**). For this reason, we ask you to consent to the video recording of the sessions. Finally, the materials will be properly edited and made publicly available on the **CoAct** website by the end of 2021.

UB OFFICIAL CERTIFICATE: You will need to attend more than 80% of the sessions to obtain a certificate of attendance. If you also want to have a grade in your certificate, then you will need to participate in the mentoring sessions and present your reflections and thoughts on Citizen Social Science on the last day of the school. Mutual learning among participants is a relevant aspect that the school would like to enhance, therefore mentoring and presentations will be conducted in small groups, open to everyone. Please, if this is your case, express your interest in receiving the school certificate when filling the form.

If you have questions regarding any issue related to the school, please send us an email to opensystems@ub.edu (Nieves Lorenzo-Gotor).

3.4 Sessions

The school includes three types of activities:

5 seminars with round tables (S) will encourage discussion, reflection, and debate. They will focus on several aspects which might not be the general rule in the academic world. Selected topics include citizen labs, makers' world, knowledge commons and public or collective experiments. These topics will surely spark broader discussions involving many other relevant topics via face-to-face exchange of visions and perspectives.

7 workshops (W) will offer a very practical basis, which in most cases will be grounded on practical experience raised by CoAct partners. Two workshops will particularly focus on our relationship with data in a playful manner and practical aspects related to open science, which we consider important aspects in the discussion on the social dimensions of Citizen Science.

4 mentoring and working together (M) sessions will allow you to be in direct contact with us as organisers of the school as well as with a selected group of mentors. The sessions will also allow you to work together with your school mates that show fabulous skills as expressed in their motivation letter and bio. You will work in small groups to strengthen specific aspects of Citizen Social Science projects related to your field, background, or interests.

Each session is documented with a bio of the lecturer(s), a short summary about the contents of each session, a description of the methodology that will be developed to moderate the session, and list of resources suggested by the lecturer(s).

3.5 Seminars with round tables

Seminars S1, S2, S3, and S4 will start with an invited speaker who will present a specific key topic during a talk of no more than 40 minutes. After that, we encourage you to turn on your camera to start a face-to-face interaction. There will be time for questions and answers from the audience but, most importantly, the debate will be enriched by two/three invited panellists/respondents that will bring new and complementary perspectives on the topic. The guest speaker will remain with us during the two hours duration of the session. Everyone is welcome to participate actively in the discussion of the round tables.

The structure of S0 and S5 will differ a bit from the other seminars. S0 will present a general perspective on Citizen Social Science provided by the CoAct project partners, S5 will provide several perspectives from other funded projects.

3.6 Workshops

Different methodologies will be applied in each of the different workshops, specifically tailored by each team of lecturers.

These are hands-on practical sessions in which you will need to design and develop different strategies related to Citizen Social Science.

2.7 Mentoring and work with small groups

There will be four sessions of mentoring and work in small groups in line with your own current research topics and interests. The small groups configuration will be based on students' profiles.

The work will be specifically planned and oriented by the school coordinator and a group of mentors that will better adjust the contents to your interests. A selected group of mentors will be available during these sessions for at least 30 min while the rest of the time several design thinking strategies will be explored to jointly focus on relevant aspects of Citizen Social Science from your own perspective, background, and context.

Each group will be focussed on a **UN Sustainable Development Goal (SDG)** related to specific social issues. A transdisciplinary approach will be encouraged to further explore and map social dimension inside the CoAct Citizen Social Science Research and Innovation Cycle (R&I cycle, see Figure 2, below). Aspects to be covered would be related to research methods in general (including research integrity, inclusion or ethics and privacy), but also practical issues such as how to run possible co-creation dynamics with a group of Co-Researchers, which is the most suitable digital platforms, what is the most adequate data collection protocol, how to collectively interpret data, and several options to bring up actionable knowledge for collective action.

Each group will finally present their own perspective to the social dimensions in the R&I cycle and in relation to SDG. The effort will contribute to the CoAct exploration on the enhancement of social dimensions in the Citizen Science R&I cycle. Presentations will all follow the same structure based on the different exercises developed in Mentoring and work with small groups sessions. Presentations will also enhance collective discussion. Your presentation with small groups and your active participation in the discussion with fellow participants can be included in your final accreditation, if you ask for UB official recognition.

Figure 3: Research and Innovation Cycle being used in CoAct. Similar versions are being followed by different Citizen Science initiatives. Mentoring and work with small groups will explore the social dimensions of this cycle.

3.8 Virtual Tools and Spaces

All sessions will be held on the **zoom** platform. You will be receiving an email with a link to the specific room.

- The Zoom room will be the same for all **Workshops** and **Seminars with round tables**. Please log in some time before the first session starts as you will need to register.
- **Workshops** may eventually be using additional digital tools, which will be specifically provided in each session.

- **Mentoring and working groups sessions** will be using a specific **ZOOM** room, different than the one used for the **Workshops** and the **Seminars with round tables**. Additionally, the **MIRO** board on-line tool will be used for the session's dynamics and to keep track of the contributions from each group. Please, register to **MIRO** before the course starts to anticipate any technical problem.

A **Moodle** in the Campus Virtual from Universitat de Barcelona will also concentrate the school resources. Those participants providing the Universitat de Barcelona required information will have access to the **Moodle** on September 13. As the school progresses, materials and resources provided by lecturers will be uploaded, even after the school ends. These materials include the session recordings that will be gradually added. The space will be available to school participants until January 2022, at least. After the school, CoAct will also leave open an edited version of all materials compiled (January 2022). Also, the current pdf will be updated with these resources, and you will have access to the newest version through a permalink.

3.9 Code of conduct and etiquette

We understand the CoAct Citizen Social Science School as an open and inclusive school, aiming to foster a horizontal debate between all participants, whatever their background or experience.

As school's coordinator, we have foreseen many spaces for debates and open discussions to promote an active participation of the participants.

We ask your collaboration to promote a horizontal and respectful atmosphere:

- Please always to have a cordial treatment
- Please respect word turns
- Please do not hoard the word for a long time
- Please do no judge other participants' inputs or opinions

All of us have some interesting experience and viewpoints to share! We are looking forward for your inputs!

Meeting Etiquette

- If your bandwidth allows, have your camera's switched on during the debates, and your microphones switched off unless you are speaking.
- If you wish to contribute to the discussions then please raise your hand (virtually) so that we can give you the word.
- Please also feel free to contribute to the discussion through the chat. We will always be there ready to answer.

3.10 Schedule

We have **9 intense afternoons**: yes, we have decided to limit screen fatigue as much as possible by shortening the daily sessions.

The schedule is from **13.30h until 18.00h (CET)**, generally including two sessions of 2 hours each, **with a 30 min break**. Please log in to the sessions five minutes before they start. We will be strict with the timing of the sessions.

WEEK 1 – 13-17 September

Time	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday
13.30	Welcome	W1: CoAct for Mental Health: sharing first-hand experiences and cocreating	W2: Digital Participation in vulnerable contexts during Covid times	W3: Methods Development for Participatory Social Research with Young	W4: The research forum as a methodological foundation in co-creational
14.00	S0: Citizen Social Science: Enhancing social dimensions in Citizen Science				
14.30					
15.00	BREAK				
15.30	BREAK				
16.00	BREAK	S1: Citizen labs for citizen innovation: opportunities and challenges	M2: Mentoring and working together	S2: Social dimensions in Citizen Science: Leveraging the knowledge commons	S3: Public and collective experiments
16.30	M1: Mentoring and working together				
17.00					
17.30					
18.00					

WEEK 2 – 20-23 September

Time CET	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday
13.30	W5: Open Science in Citizen Social Science projects	W6: Play with Data	W7: Participatory Evaluation in Citizen Social Science	S5: Putting Citizen Social Science experiences together
14.00				
14.30				
15.00	BREAK			
15.30	BREAK			
16.00	S4: Knowledge Production with Makers	M3: Mentoring and working together	M4: Mentoring and working together	Presentations and final discussion
16.30				
17.00				
17.30				
18.00				

S: Seminar with Round Table

W: Workshop

Day 1 - Monday, September 13th, 2021

Time (CET)

13.30-14.00h **Welcome. Meeting each other**

Josep Perelló and Nieves Lorenzo-Gotor, Universitat de Barcelona

14.00-16.00h **S0: Citizen Social Science: Enhancing social dimensions in Citizen Science**

CoAct partners

Break

16.30-18.00h **M1: Mentoring and working together**

Day 2 – Tuesday, September 14th, 2021

13.30-15.30h **W1: CoAct for Mental Health: sharing first-hand experiences and co-creating a chatbot for a Citizen Social Science research**

Anna Cigarini, Isabelle Bonhoure, and Franziska Peter, Universitat de Barcelona

Break

16.00-18.00h **S1: Citizen labs for citizen innovation: opportunities and challenges**

Main speaker: Juan Freire, Tecnológico de Monterrey. Round table: Marcos Garcia, Madrid Medialab Prado cofounder; Paco González, IN3, Universitat Oberta de Catalunya.

Day 3 – Wednesday, September 15th, 2021

13.30-15.30h **W2: Digital Participation in vulnerable contexts during Covid times**

Valeria Arza, Guillermina Actis, Leticia Castro, Malena Velarde, Universidad Nacional de San Martín

Break

16.00-18.00h **M2: Mentoring and working together**

Day 4 – Thursday, September 16th, 2021

13.30-15.30h **W3: Methods Development for Participatory Social Research with Young People**

Veronika Wöhrer and Teresa Wintersteller, University of Vienna

Break

16.00-18.00h **S2: Social Dimensions in Citizen Science: Leveraging the knowledge commons**

Shannon Dosemagen, Shuttleworth Foundation Fellow and Director, Open Environmental Data Project. Round table: Evelin Heidel, Climate Change Wikiproject; Pia Marchegiani, Fundación Ambiente y Recursos Naturales (FARN);

Raffaele Ippolito, University of Oxford; Anna Cigarini (moderator), Universitat de Barcelona

Day 5 – Friday, September 17th, 2021

13.30-15.30h **W4: The research forum as a methodological foundation for communication and participation in co-creational CSS**

David Scheller, Stefan Thomas, Potsdam University of Applied Sciences

Break

16.00-18.00h **S3: Public and collective experiments**

Josep Perelló, Universitat de Barcelona. Round table: Chris Salter, University of Concordia; Amanda Masha Caminals, Matadero Madrid

Day 6 – Monday, September 20th, 2021

13.30-15.30h **W5: Open Science in Citizen Social Science projects: general framework and practical guidelines**

Katja Mayer, Centre for Social Innovation and University of Vienna
Ignasi Labastida, Universitat de Barcelona

Break

16.00-17.00h **S4: Knowledge Production with Makers: Situatedness, Infrastructuring and Critical Practice**

Regina Sipos, Technical University of Berlin, Institute of Vocational Education and Work Studies. Round table: Irene Agrivina, HONF Foundation; Saad Chinoy, Engineering Good; Georgia Nicolau, Procomum Institute

Day 7 – Tuesday, September 21st, 2021

13.30-15.30h **W6: Play with Data**

Pau Garcia, Natalia Santolaria, Domestic Data Streamers

Break

16.00-18.00h **M3: Mentoring and Working together**

Day 8 – Wednesday, September 22nd, 2021

13.30-15.30h **W7: Participatory Evaluation in Citizen Social Science**

Katja Mayer, Stefanie Schürz, Centre for Social Innovation

Break

16.00-18.00h **M4: Mentoring and working together**

Day 9 – Thursday, September 23rd, 2021

13.30-15.30h **S5: Putting Citizen Social Science experiences together: YouCount, COESO, SoCis, ActEarly and CoAct**

Reidun Norvoll, Aina Landsverk Hagen, Oslo Metropolitan University;
Alessia Smaniotto, OpenEdition; Claudia Göbel, Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg; Alexandra Albert, University College of London; Josep Perelló, Universitat de Barcelona

Break

16.00-18.00h **Public students' presentations**

Different groups of school participants

End of the school

Day 1 - Monday, September 13

13.30-14.00h. Welcome. Meeting each other

Josep Perelló and Nieves Lorenzo-Gotor, Universitat de Barcelona

Welcome and kick-off by the school coordinators. You will be given a brief overview of the contents of the course and its dynamics. Meet your new classmates!

14.00-16.00h. S0: Citizen Social Science: Enhancing social dimensions in Citizen Science

Josep Perelló and Isabelle Bonhoure, Universitat de Barcelona

David Scheller, Potsdam University of Applied Sciences (FHP)

In this session, Citizen Science will be introduced jointly with the current discussions on how social dimension shall be considered and on how academics from the social sciences are currently shaping Citizen Social Science. CoAct vision will also be introduced. CoAct understands Citizen Social Science as participatory research co-designed and directly driven by citizen groups sharing a social concern. It combines equal collaboration between citizen groups (Co-Researchers) that share a social concern, and academic researchers. The session will end up with a summary of the State-of-the-Art CoAct deliverable.

16.30-18.00h. M1: Mentoring and working together*

During this first mentoring session, you will choose your own working group for the following days. Grouped by your research interests, you will learn from the different backgrounds and context of your mates. In this session you will get an idea of the interests of all school participants. We will propose networking tools that you can explore to connect and create synergies. Within your working group, you will deepen on your ideas and expectations of the school. The final objective of the mentoring sessions is to present all

* Only to those that expressed their will to participate to these sessions.

your reflections, ideas of applicability and wonders regarding social dimensions in Citizen Science. For that, you will start shaping your group presentation in this session.

Day 2 – Tuesday, September 14

13.30-15.30h. W1: CoAct for Mental Health: sharing first-hand experiences and co-creating a chatbot for a Citizen Social Science research

Anna Cigarini, Isabelle Bonhoure and Franziska Peter, Universitat de Barcelona.

This workshop will simulate the co-design process of the CoAct for Mental Health project. In the project, both non-digital (a research diary) and digital (a chatbot) tools are used to place individuals with an experience of mental health and relatives at the centre of the research. During the workshop, you will have the opportunity to use the research diary to write down and share personal experiences of social support during the COVID pandemic. Further, you will see how your personal stories can be included in a chatbot to map social support resources and strategies worldwide. After a practical hands-on test of the digital and non-digital tools, you will be invited to discuss the potentials and limitations of the research diary and the chatbot for supporting participatory research projects with concerned communities.

METHODOLOGY

You will be provided with the research diary, and, after a brief overview of digital storytelling/conversational design, you will be asked to share one/two personal story/es of social support in the context of the covid pandemic. The second part of the session will be showing key elements that any chatbot in the field of citizen science should have. Finally, the session will close with a general discussion on the tools showcased and how similar strategies could be used in Citizen Social Science projects. You will learn how to get from the blank paper to a functioning chatbot and which different fields of knowledge and skill are necessary. The one or two personal stories from the research diary will serve as examples for chatbot content that aims at mapping social support networks in times of the Covid pandemic. Finally, the session will close with a general discussion on the tools showcased and how similar strategies could be used in citizen social science projects.

RESOURCES

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4. Senabre, E., Ferran Ferrer, N., & Perelló, J. "Participatory Design of Citizen Science Experiments." 2018, vol. 26, no. 54, pp. 29-38, <https://doi.org/10.3916/C54-2018-03>

16.00-18.00h. S1: Citizen labs for citizen innovation: opportunities and challenges

Juan Freire, Universidad Tecmilenio

Round Table with

Marcos Garcia, Madrid Medialab Prado former director/founder

Paco González, IN3, Universitat Oberta de Catalunya

In this seminar, citizen innovation is proposed as a special category of social innovation with specific characteristics and, hopefully, different approaches to problems and results: the diversity of participants engaging effectively the people affected by problems and challenges; the integration of multiple epistemologies without an *a priori* hierarchy of stakeholders; the key role of mediation; and processes based in continuous experimentation and prototyping. Citizen labs are devices engaging citizens and impulse citizen innovation and could be discovered in many forms, from institutions to communities that organize themselves using the rules of citizen innovation. The lecturer will present strategic elements for a real empowering of innovation in labs: rules to assure openness, tools and programs,

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governance and legal status, funding to assure autonomy and sustainability, essential infrastructures, and mediation. Finally, some of the main challenges for the citizen lab format will also be discussed: their relationship with the commons; how to scale the format and their impact; and how to use this logic to develop public policies based in experimentation and the inclusion of citizen diversity and perspectives.

The discussion will introduce citizen laboratories as a model of institution that can facilitate the creation of citizen science projects. Institutions that we have inherited such as universities, libraries, town halls, schools or health centers, can enable stable programs of citizen laboratories for the development of projects open to any participation and that seek to improve life together. The potential of these programs will be greater to the extent that they are able to collaborate with each other both locally and internationally.

RESOURCES

1. Citizen Innovation labs: Emergency, model, formats
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342664748_Laboratorios_de_innovacion_ciudadana_Emergencia_modelo_formatos
2. The art of documenting
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/329515122_El_arte_de_documentar
3. slowU: a transformation proposal from the University
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349831658_slowU_una_propuesta_de_transformacion_de_la_Universidad
4. Smith, R. C., Bossen, C., & Kanstrup, A. M. (2017). Participatory design in an era of participation. *CoDesign*, 13(2), 65–69.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15710882.2017.1310466>
5. Slavin, K. (2016). Design as Participation. *Journal of Design and Science*.
<https://doi.org/10.21428/a39a747c>
6. Collaborating, Experimenting, Sharing. Welcome to Medialab Prado
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rNhVp7uhz6w>

Day 3 – Wednesday, September 15

13.30-15.30h. W2: Digital Participation in vulnerable contexts during Covid times

Valeria Arza, Guillermina Actis, Leticia Castro and Malena Velarde, Universidad Nacional de San Martín (UNSAM)

Citizen science actions in vulnerable contexts were very much affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. This session aims to share strategies to cope with the different challenges involved in launching these actions. Together with other students and lecturers, you will collectively reflect about research issues of the initial stages in Citizen Science research cycles: i) designing informed consent procedures; ii) building a collaborative virtual environment to host co-researchers, community groups, NGOs and academic teams and iii) implementing co-evaluation activities.

METHODOLOGY

Using a world-cafe approach, you will join three rounds to discuss the best strategies that the action organisers should follow to consider your selected stakeholder profiles' needs related to the **three citizen social science research activities**. The facilitator will start the discussion at each round by presenting the breakout room citizen social science research activity and the questions to be discussed and she will also summarise the previous round of participants' insights. To take notes on these discussions, we will use a **Miro** digital board. At the end of the exercise, you will have covered all three citizen social science research activities and participated in discussions regarding potential problems and solutions. In the plenary session, facilitators will summarize the main discussions and consensus on the issues, presenting the boards and with the possibility of participants to intervene. Then, we will invite all participants to share their thoughts through a Mentimeter to collect their reflections on the general topic of the workshop.

RESOURCES

1. Actis and Velarde (2021, February 1st). Wrapping up CoAct Riachuelo's 2020: Co-designing a Citizen Social Science project in the COVID-19 context in Argentina. CoAct

Blog. <https://coactproject.eu/news/wrapping-up-coact-riachuelos-2020-co-designing-a-citizen-social-science-project-in-the-covid-19-context-in-argentina/>

2. Arza, Actis, Marchegiani, Velarde, Cane, Buchsbaum, Swistun, Deliverable 5.1 Report on Knowledge Coalition Building. Environmental Justice, CoAct.
https://zenodo.org/record/4443441#.YLjg2_kzaUk
3. Brown, T., & Wyatt, J. (2015). Design thinking for social innovation. Annual Review of Policy Design, 3(1), 1-10. <https://ojs.unbc.ca/index.php/design/article/view/1272/1089>
4. IDEO, (2011). Human-Centered Design Toolkit: An Open-Source Toolkit To Inspire New Solutions in the Developing World, IDEO. <https://www.ideo.com/post/design-kit>

16.30-18.00h. M2: Mentoring and working together

In this second mentoring session, you will debate the topics covered for the moment within your working group. You will discuss the steps of the Citizen Social Science research and innovation cycle with your group mates, according to your common interests and adding your different views within the context of SDGs and in terms of your background. You will also have the opportunity to discuss your group thoughts and ideas with other school participants. Moreover, you will present and get feedback from school lecturers that will be available as mentors. You will be collecting all the reflections and learned lessons, starting to shape them for the final presentation. You and your group will agree on a common virtual workspace to stay in touch and share all ideas and information gathered. This platform is intended to help you working remotely with your mates and you can use it beyond the mentoring sessions.

Day 4 – Thursday, September 16

13.30-15.30h. W3: Methods development for participatory social research with young people

Veronika Wöhrer and Teresa Wintersteller, Universität Wien

In this workshop you will discuss how to develop and adjust digital and non-digital social science research methods that can be used in participatory action research with young people. In Austria, young people until the age of 18, who neither attend school nor pursue an apprenticeship have to attend measures that offer educational and social skills training as well as support them in finding a suitable place in education or training. At the University of Vienna, the speakers do participatory research with young people attending these measures to reflect on the needs of youth in this socio-political support structure. The research is accompanied by a Knowledge Coalition of stakeholders who are responsible in implementing and developing the measures for young people, to ensure an interaction between the co-researchers and the responsible policy stakeholders.

The topic and context of this case study will be presented. You will learn about the dynamics in the knowledge coalition as well as methods developed over the years to make social science research accessible and usable for young people, who are normally addressed educationally disadvantaged. Two methods will be introduced in more detail: situational analysis and the digital tool **Actionbound**.

METHODOLOGY

You will work in small groups to try out and reflect on the use of the two methods. In the plenary you will discuss how to engage young people in social science research.

RESOURCES

1. Arztmann, D.; Wintersteller, T.; Wöhrer, V. (2016): 'Do Differences Destroy a "We"?' Producing Knowledge with Children and Young People In: Graduate Journal of Social Science April 2016, Vol. 12 (2), pp. 77–95.

<http://gjss.org/sites/default/files/issues/chapters/papers/GJSS%20Vol%2012-2%204%20Arztmann%20et%20al.pdf>

2. Davidson, E. (2017): Saying It Like It Is? Power, Participation and Research Involving Young People. In: Social Inclusion 5.2, 228-239.
3. Wöhrer, V.; Höcher, B. (2012): Tricks of the Trade. Negotiations and Dealings of Researchers, Pupils and Teachers, in: Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung (FQS) Vol.13 (1).
<http://www.qualitative-research.net/index.php/fqs/article/view/1797>

16.00-18.00h. S2: Social dimensions in Citizen Science: Leveraging the knowledge commons

Shannon Dosemagen, Shuttleworth Foundation fellow

Round Table moderated by Anna Cigarini and with

Evelin Heidel, Climate Change Wikiproject

Pia Marchegiani, FARN

Raffaele Ippolito, University of Oxford

The production of knowledge that is openly accessible, easy to find and has clear routes for usability, is part of the critical infrastructure of engaging with the most pressing environmental issues of our day – from the climate crisis to industrial pollution to biodiversity and cultural loss. This seminar will focus on how the field of “open” has both contributed to and faced challenges in constructively providing a new toolset for citizen and community science practitioners and researchers. It will look at where social dimensions of citizen science have advanced the ability for communities to productively ask questions about, and find solutions to, local issues, while at the same time exploring where the knowledge commons can work better. Seminar participants will be asked to engage in a discussion on the challenges faced in ensuring that different facets of the knowledge commons - from data and information to the technical tools that we use to collect and gather – are useful and usable in supporting practitioners and researchers in achieving their goals.

The respondents will be introducing several additional experiences. FARN (Fundación Ambiente y Recursos Naturales) promotes sustainable development through law, policy and the institutional organization of society. Citizen participation is at the centre of FARNs work, which seeks to integrate citizens in decision-making at all level in different processes involving environmental and development policy. Moreover, as most environmental issues and conflicts relate to the need to discuss modes of extraction, production and consumption of goods, and in many cases, challenge mainstream policy assumptions, science plays a key role. As such, science in general, and social sciences in particularly, when they are in an open form, which otherwise not accessible, can help citizens bring issues and arguments to different policy instances. Also, the experiences of industrial pollution and illness in fenceline communities in Italy and Taiwan, with a focus on the slow dimension of toxic exposure in the everyday life of residents. Finally, some of the biggest threats that we're seeing right now altering the public discourse on the climate crisis are part of the failed promises of open: misinformation, extremism, political radicalization, enclosure of the public conversation, among many others. The promise of digital technologies of more information and the democratization of knowledge hasn't brought us closer to achieving the goal of a more equitable society. We need to critically rethink how the ethos of radical openness and transparency can be applied to the climate crisis and what it means for our current movement. Open has a role to play in the climate crisis, but it's worth exploring what that role could be.

RESOURCES

1. Open Climate Now. (2021) Dosemagen, S., Heidel, E., Murillo, L.F.R., Velis, E., Stinson, A., Thorne, M. In Branch Magazine, Issue 2.
2. Open Hardware: An opportunity to build better science. (2021) Parker, A., Dosemagen, S., Bowser, A., Novak, A. Report for the Wilson Center Science and Technology Innovation Program.
3. For a People Centered Science: A Call to Action. (2019) Dosemagen, S. In Science for the People: Envisioning and Enacting the Science We Need, vol.22(2).
4. <https://www.shannondosemagen.com/writing>

Day 5 – Friday, September 17

13.30-15.30h. W4: The research forum as a methodological foundation for communication and participation in co-creational CSS

Stefan Thomas and David Scheller, Potsdam University of Applied Sciences (FHP)

This workshop will present the research forum as a horizontal and safe communicative space moderated by academic researchers that enables co-researcher participation across all phases of co-creational research projects. We argue that in co-creational citizen social science, such a communicative space requires conceptualisation for it to foster citizens' engagement in the knowledge production that deals with their specific social lifeworlds. In the research forum, the potential that the social sciences bring to citizen science—methodological reflection and the theoretical interpretation and contextualisation of data—can flourish in a collaborative process. The research forum suggests four central dimensions to promote participatory research: (1) opening spaces for social encounters; (2) establishing communicative practice; (3) initiating a process of social self-understanding; (4) engaging in (counter-)public discourses. You will discuss the potential and challenges of the research forum in which academic and co-researcher collaborate on a mutual research topic.

You will ideate approaches to establishing safe spaces and open communication between the stakeholders of the research, gaining new understanding of social research topics, and developing social interventions based on new knowledge and insights in your own research.

METHODOLOGY

Speakers will present a conceptualisation of the research forum as a communicative space to foster co-creation. In small groups, you will reflect your experiences and expectations in your own research, regarding participatory and communicative research approaches. In the plenary you will discuss the general findings of the working groups on how to engage with citizens in social science research.

RESOURCES

1. Bergold, J. & Thomas, S. (2012). Participatory Research Methods: A Methodological Approach in Motion Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung/Forum: Qualitative Social Research, 13(1). <http://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:0114-fqs1201302>
2. Thomas, S., Scheller, D., & Schröder, S. (forthcoming). Co-creation in citizen social science: the research forum as a methodological foundation for communication and participation. Humanities & Social Science Communications.
3. Kemmis, S., & McTaggart, R. (2005). Participatory Action Research: Communicative Action and the Public Sphere. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Research (pp. 559–603). Thousand Oaks, Cf: Sage.

16.00-18.00h. S3: Public and collective experiments

Josep Perelló, Universitat de Barcelona

Round table with

Chris Salter, Concordia University, Hexagram, Montreal

Amanda Masha Caminals, Instituto Mutante, Matadero Madrid

Behind each citizen social science initiative, there is always a particular history, and each field of knowledge can also give life to a different citizen science. More specifically, in computational social science and complexity sciences (Perelló et al., 2012; Sagarra et al., 2016) there is a need to overcome the current opaque data sources (with social networks as the main paradigm, using data from technological companies) and come up with a wilder type of research (outside the laboratory, one that is more representative and closer to everyday life). Laboratory work needs to simplify reality and decontextualise it somehow, which is useful to build universal and reproducible knowledge, but can also fail in its desire to address and help address immediate social challenges.

In this seminar, we delve into a particular approach to study human behaviour in public space. During last 9 years, OpenSystems has been formalising public experiments that try to respond to localised and contextualised social concerns (Sagarra et al., 2016). Using digital

devices (Vicens, Perelló, et al., 2018), laboratory methodologies can take the streets. The experiment transforms into an experience thanks to an urban listening device. Passers-by and neighbours who want to participate reflect for some minutes about an issue related to a shared concern in the community, collective, or specific group of citizens have codesigned under the form of collective and public experiment.

People cease to be mere passive experimental subjects and the obtained data are valuable at least for the community behind the project, formed by people who want to know the reaction of their fellow citizens to a specific social problem. The results were valuable to highlight inherent inequities in climate change action (Vicens et al., 2018), the different social roles in community mental health care (Cigarini et al., 2018), or gendered aspects of street social interactions (Cigarini et al., 2020), to mention just a few examples that have already been published in high-impact scientific journals.

Co-creation spaces can be schools, prisons, or libraries and their communities (groups of classmates, inmates, or users). And the people who occupy these spaces are the ones who help define the research topic and the most relevant research questions, and will also interpret the data, together with the scientists. Meanwhile, the public spaces for the experiments can be game festivals (DAU Barcelona in several editions), street art festivals (FiraTàrrrega 2017, in their opening show or Escena Poblenou 2018), or science festivals (the science biennale organised by the Culture Institute of Barcelona, with the collaboration of a theatre company and a school of design). But they can also pop up for a few days or hours on the busiest boulevards or squares.

During the round table, we will discuss topics such as what are the terms of the ecological transition that we must undertake? How might cultural institutions act as propositional devices to face it? What role can art, science and citizen participation play on that? Today, more than ever, we need initiatives that help us foster our collective imagination with the possibility of non-dystopic futures and our responsibility towards future generations of humans and non-humans. Mutant devices that propose, support, and amplify interdisciplinary initiatives and citizen science strategies weaving resilient communities.

Along similar lines, another topic that will be discussed is the international trend to harness new relationships between the sciences and the arts to address the wicked problems of our times: climate emergency, rising inequality, technological disruption, and transformation. Such relationships might have two important aims: to alter existing ways of thinking about the nature of art(s) and science(s) and, perhaps more importantly, transform the relations between artists and scientists and their objects and publics. This mutual transformation can result in a new form of affective citizen engagement what anthropologist Georgina Born calls the “public experiment.” Such public experiments are not about communicating established (“preformed”) scientific (or artistic) knowledge to a pre-existing public. It is about “producing new relations between knowledge, things, locations and persons that did not exist before.” In other words, the transformative potential of forging these new connections is that the private objects of research can be transformed into collective ones, constituted with and through publics rather than being simply transmitted and transferred to them.

RESOURCES

1. Cigarini, A., Vicens, J., & Perelló, J. (2020). Gender-based pairings influence cooperative expectations and behaviours. *Scientific Reports*, 10(1), 1-10.
2. Bonhoure, I., Cigarini, A., Vicens, J., & Perelló, J. (2019). Citizen Social Science in practice: a critical analysis of a mental health community-based project. Preprint osf.io DOI: 10.31235/osf.io/63aj7
3. Cigarini, A., Vicens, J., Duch, J., Sánchez, A., & Perelló, J. (2018). **Quantitative account of social interactions in a mental health care ecosystem: cooperation, trust and collective action.** *Scientific Reports*, 8(1), 1-9.
4. Vicens, J., Perelló, J., & Duch, J. (2018). **Citizen Social Lab: A digital platform for human behavior experimentation within a citizen science framework.** *PloS one*, 13(12), e0207219.
5. Senabre, E., Ferran-Ferrer, N., & Perelló, J. (2018). **Participatory design of citizen science experiments.** *Comunicar. Media Education Research Journal*, 26(1).

6. Vicens, J., Bueno-Guerra, N., Gutiérrez-Roig, M., Gracia-Lázaro, C., Gómez-Gardeñes, J., Perelló, J., Sánchez, A., Moreno, Y. & Duch, J. (2018). **Resource heterogeneity leads to unjust effort distribution in climate change mitigation.** *PloS one*, 13(10), e0204369.
7. Callon, M., Lascoumes, P., & Barthe, Y. (2011). *Acting in an uncertain world: An essay on technical democracy.* Inside Technology.
8. Latour, B. (2004). *Politics of nature.* Harvard University Press.
9. Salter, C. (2010). *Entangled: technology and the transformation of performance.* MIT Press.
10. Salter, C., & Pickering, A. (2015). *Alien agency: Experimental encounters with art in the making.* MIT Press.
11. Citizen Science Toolkit from StemForYouth EU Project <http://www.stem4youth.eu/citizen-science>
12. OpenSystems webpage <http://www.ub.edu/opensystems>
13. <https://ars.electronica.art/newdigitaldeal/de/emergence-y/>
14. <https://www.routledge.com/Routledge-Handbook-of-Art-Science-and-Technology-Studies/Rogers-Halpern-Hannah-Ridder-Vignone/p/book/9781138347304>
15. <https://sfdora.org/>
16. <https://www.gridspinoza.net/en/node/187>
17. [https://www.academia.edu/15463022/Interdisciplinarity Reconfigurations of the Social and Natural Sciences 2013](https://www.academia.edu/15463022/Interdisciplinarity_Reconfigurations_of_the_Social_and_Natural_Sciences_2013)

WEEKEND BREAK!

Day 6 – Monday, September 20

13.30-15.30h. W5: Open Science in Citizen Social Science projects: general framework and practical guidelines

Ignasi Labastida, Universitat de Barcelona

Katja Mayer, Center for Social Innovation and Universität Wien

The session will have an introductory presentation to provide a broad overview of open science before focusing on sharing data in Citizen Science and Citizen Social Science.

Open Science is normally understood as the opening of research processes and scientific findings. Citizen Science is opening science towards participation and deliberation. You will discuss the mutual benefits of open science and citizen science for next generation researchers. Open Science in general, and Citizen Science in particular, do not only change the *modus operandi* of research, they also teach us a lot about science: They address both the necessary changes of scientific conduct but also what matters for a science that is deeply embedded in society.

Sharing data is a core area of Open Science and is also increasingly being addressed in Citizen Science. What do you need to pay attention to when collecting and processing data if it is to be shared or opened immediately or later? Who benefits from this data? What quality criteria must the data obey to be further usable?

The second part of this session will address two very practical issues: How to make your own Data Management Plan? Where to publish your results? Make your Data Management Plan (DMP): Many funders and institutions are requiring researchers to deliver a data management plan at the beginning of a project or a PhD thesis. This requirement sometimes is seen as an extra burden for researchers. However, the creation of a DMP can help researchers organizing the data they will work with or they will create. Moreover, the DMP can help researchers in solving some issues like the storage of data, the share of responsibilities, the related legal aspects or how to disseminate the data.

Publishing your results: The scholarly communication landscape has changed in the last decade. Beside traditional journals and publishers, there are now several options to choose when you decide to disseminate your research results. There are all kind of preprint servers, new publishing platforms that provide an open peer review, repositories to share our publications and all the open access options. As researcher you need to choose the right option considering your research career, the requirements of funders, and your commitment to share your results broadly. In this part of the session, you will analyse all the concerns about publishing preprints before having an article accepted, how to place the right version in a repository or how much will cost you to publish in an open access journal.

METHODOLOGY

The session will first (during 30 minutes) provide a theoretical perspective to open science in the context of Citizen Science and Citizen Social Science. The rest of the session wants to help you to develop your own DMP based in your actual research based on initial feedback and by using a case study. You will review all the steps to create the plan and you will adapt it to your specifications. Finally, there will be an open debate on where to publish the results of a research.

RESOURCES

1. Bezjak, S., Clyburne-Sherin, A., Conzett, P., Fernandes, P. L., Görögh, E., Helbig, K., Kramer, B., Labastida, I., Niemeyer, K., Psomopoulos, F., & Tennant, J. (2018). The open science training handbook. TIB. <https://open-science-training-handbook.gitbook.io/>
2. de Sherbinin, A., Bowser, A., Chuang, T.-R., Cooper, C., Danielsen, F., Edmunds, R., Elias, P., Faustman, E., Hultquist, C., Mondardini, R., Popescu, I., Shonowo, A., & Sivakumar, K. (2021). The Critical Importance of Citizen Science Data. *Frontiers in Climate*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fclim.2021.650760>
3. Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission). (2018). Turning FAIR into reality: Final report and action plan from the European Commission expert group on FAIR data. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/1524>

4. Hecker, S., Haklay, M., Bowser, A., Makuch, Z., Vogel, J., & Bonn, A. (2018). Innovation in open science, society and policy—setting the agenda for citizen science. *Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy*. UCL Press, London, UK, 1–23. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctv550cf2.8>
5. Wehn, U., Gobel, C., Bowser, A., Hepburn, L., & Haklay, M. (2020). Global citizen science perspectives on open science. <http://pure.iiasa.ac.at/id/eprint/16729/>
6. Williams, J., Chapman, C., Leibovici, D., Loïs, G., Matheus, A., Oggioni, A., Schade, S., See, L., & van Genuchten, P. (2018). Maximising the impact and reuse of citizen science data. *JSTOR*. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctv550cf2.29>

16.00-18.00h. S4: Knowledge production with makers: Situatedness, infrastructuring and critical practice

Regina Sipos, Technical University of Berlin

Round Table with

Irene Agrivina, HONF Foundation

Saad Chinoy, Engineering Good

Georgia Nicolau, Procomum Institute

Grassroots innovation, and especially maker communities have been getting increasing attention in this “era of participation” we are experiencing. Makers have been praised for their innovation capabilities, entrepreneurial spirit, for sharing blueprints openly, and many more aspects. This session focuses on 3 emerging research topics and reflects upon them through the lens of knowledge production and post-colonial computing. First, the situatedness of making will be discussed, with a special focus on maker culture as a "global assemblage", locating and understanding the heterogeneous, situated and diverse "maker movement" around the world, and different types of knowledge production methods. Then, infrastructuring in grassroots communities will be examined, considering both physical infrastructures (e.g., access to platforms or lack thereof, and matters of privacy) and the

human communities that act as infrastructures, producing knowledge as they advance. Finally, critical and socially innovative technical practice will be highlighted, and how knowledge is produced through the practice.

The discussion will incorporate different perspectives and topics. On the one hand, there is a lot of knowledge and creative capacity of civil society to produce scientific knowledge and technology- and the non-professionalized participation in science is not something new as Lafuente, Frissoli and Parra write “the production of scientific knowledge has never been an exclusive practice of scientists, much less professionalized. Workers, technicians, sailors and explorers, hunters and amateur naturalists, domestic caregivers and philanthropists have volunteered at various times to collect and classify data”. On the other hand, there is an over-concentration of scientific data and information in universities and public organizations. These capabilities are usually not combined into socially transformative actions. The generation of new, more open and democratic services and processes, in close connection with the needs of their interlocutors, could be greatly enhanced through joint production of knowledge and information by universities, public authorities and civil society.

The lockdown situation in response to the pandemic has seen a dramatic rise in maker participation beyond the tech. With the critical shortage of PPE forcing the need for alternatives, "good enough engineering" served many while large scale production ramped up. Access to the internet and digital devices were also seen as essential. While the tangible objects produced by the maker response may not have directly saved many lives but the makers, engineers, tinkerers, hobbyists, geeks, and others stepped up to volunteer supported the frontline healthcare workers and those that were not supported by established systems. While the needs are no longer immediate and the response is largely seen as temporary, the people remain engaged in new and meaningful ways that are yet to be understood. The pandemic is global, as is the digital perspective but we're not through it yet and without engaged people what good are all the high-tech, cutting edge, AI powered technologies?

Finally, HONF experience will be presented. HONF started as a collective in 1999 in Yogyakarta, Indonesia, as a place of open expression, art and cultural technologies in the wake of the Indonesian "revolution". HONF aka the 'House of Natural Fiber' was born out of the social and political turmoil against the Suharto regime, its nepotism and governmental corruption. They run various programs, activities, research and projects under their curriculum called EFP (Education Focus Program) which focuses on the application and practical use in daily life of collaborative, cross-disciplinary and technological actions responding to social, cultural and environmental challenges. EFP is a response to the needs of societies in development and transition. As the collective became bigger, and in 2003 they established a media laboratory focusing on arts, science and technology based on an open community with interdisciplinary background. In 2011 they established themselves as a foundation, HONF Foundation hosted three labs; v.u.f.o.c an extraterrestrial study centre, HONFablab a digital fabrication lab and HONF factory a digital culture and media forum. In 2020 they established Indonesian centre for arts, science and technology and actively run their communities, programs and activities.

RESOURCES

1. Smith, Adrian, Fressoli, Mariano, and Thomas, Hernán. Grassroots innovation movements: challenges and contributions, *Journal of Cleaner Production* (2013), <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2012.12.025>
2. Debora de Castro Leal, Angelika Strohmayer, and Max Krüger. 2021. On Activism and Academia: Reflecting Together and Sharing Experiences Among Critical Friends. In CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '21), May 8–13, 2021, Yokohama, Japan. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 18 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3411764.3445263>
3. Lindtner, Silvia, Shaowen Bardzell, and Jeffrey Bardzell. 2016. "Reconstituting the Utopian Vision of Making: HCI After Technosolutionism." In Proceedings of the 2016 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '16), 1390–1402. New York: ACM.

4. Vasillis Vlachokyriakos, Clara Crivellaro, Pete Wright, and Patrick Olivier. 2018. Infrastructuring the Solidarity Economy: Unpacking Strategies and Tactics in Designing Social Innovation. In Proceedings of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '18). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Paper 481, 1–12. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3173574.3174055>
5. FROM DIGITAL EXCLUSION TO UNIVERSAL DIGITAL ACCESS IN SINGAPORE <https://fass.nus.edu.sg/ssr/wp-content/uploads/sites/8/2021/01/Digital-Access-20210118.pdf>
6. EngineeringGood Computers Against Covid
 - a. <https://engineeringgood.org/cac/>
 - b. <https://a4ai.org/research/covid-19-policy-brief-internet-access-and-affordability/>
7. Maker Asylum <https://www.makersasylum.com/m19-initiative/>
8. 3D printers in Singapore respond to support healthcare workers <https://www.channelnewsasia.com/singapore/covid-19-surgical-masks-discomfort-ear-savers-667221>
9. Makers Making Change <https://www.makersmakingchange.com/>
10. <https://honf.org>

Day 7 – Tuesday, September 21

13.30-15.30h. W6: Play with Data

Pau Garcia and Natalia Santolaria, Domestic Data Streamers

Images and pictures grab our attention and affect us emotionally in ways that text alone usually cannot. Visual metaphors, in particular — because they contextualize information — can ensure faster and far richer data processing. These visual metaphors are capable of evoking related ideas and stories, of appealing to us at both the conscious and subconscious levels, affecting us at the perceptual, cognitive and reflective levels, and of eventually captivating our mind. So what happens when, in displaying data, facts and figures, we adopt visual metaphors, instead of relying on the more traditional text-and-chart presentation strategies? In this workshop we explore and push the boundaries of data visualization and visual storytelling, to create micro-data stories that will explode in the audience's eyes and mind.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology relies on four main steps: a small lecture on data physicalization examples and projects on the field of data visualization, then a series of exercises using very basic analysis of the general tools of data physicalization and later on a small project on the analysis of an editorial piece in smaller groups; presentation of the results by each group; and finally, a brainstorm session around what could be improved in each data visualization.

RESOURCES

1. <http://giorgialupi.com/data-humanism-my-manifesto-for-a-new-data-wold>
2. https://www.ted.com/talks/aaron_koblin_visualizing_ourselves_with_crowd_sourced_data#t-625886
3. https://www.ted.com/talks/david_mccandless_the_beauty_of_data_visualization
4. <https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/34890015-factfulness>

16.00-18.00h. M3: Mentoring and working together

You will retake the mentoring sessions and have time to discuss about all the contents of the school covered until the moment. You will be working with your group to incorporate all your new ideas and perspectives to your final presentation. You will revise the Citizen Social Science research and innovation cycle, with special attention on co-creation dynamics, suitability, and adequacy to make citizen co-researchers participate. You will expose your group findings and main topics of interest to other school participants. When you listen and comment on others' explanations, you will focus on research integrity, inclusion, ethics, privacy... Finally, you will have the opportunity to meet mentors to get feedback and solve doubts. Remember to incorporate all interesting concepts to your group virtual workspace.

Day 8 – Wednesday, September 22

13.30-15.30h. W7: Participatory Evaluation in Citizen Social Science

Katja Mayer and Stefanie Schuerz, Centre for Social Innovation (ZSI)

This session will address the topic of research evaluation, and in particular project evaluation. Evaluation is generally about assessing the achievement of objectives. Here, however, the goal can lie both in the research process - for example, through the evaluation of the methods used - and in the project results. In the field of Citizen Science, however, there are many different participants with different interests and goals. How can these be fairly and inclusively targeted and evaluated?

While Citizen Science is by definition highly participatory, its evaluation and impact assessment practices traditionally fail to live up to this claim. In this session you will explore some approaches to participatory evaluation that involve participants in Citizen Science activities in reflecting on and evaluating the processes and outcomes of projects or initiatives. This involvement can range from co-designing the evaluation strategy to creating evaluation or monitoring tools to be used during and after the project, to name a few.

METHODOLOGY

In the first part, you will get a short introduction to traditional research evaluation in Citizen Science and few selected methods of participatory evaluation. In the second part, you will work in groups on your own Citizen Social Science projects and discuss how you could apply the principles of participatory evaluation there.

RESOURCES

1. Schaefer, T., Kieslinger, B., Brandt, M., & van den Bogaert, V. (2021). Evaluation in Citizen Science: The Art of Tracing a Moving Target. In K. Vohland, A. Land-Zandstra, L. Ceccaroni, R. Lemmens, J. Perelló, M. Ponti, R. Samson, & K. Wagenknecht (Eds.), *The Science of Citizen Science* (pp. 495–514). Springer International Publishing.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_25

2. Heigl, F., Kieslinger, B., Paul, K. T., Uhlik, J., Frigerio, D., & Dörler, D. (2020). Co-Creating and Implementing Quality Criteria for Citizen Science. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 5(1), 23. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.294>

Toolkits

1. Health Nexus Sante CAN. (2018). Participatory Evaluation Toolkit. Best Start. <https://resources.beststart.org/product/j24e-participatory-evaluation-toolkit-manual/>
2. Healthcare Improvement Scotland. (2019, May 23). Participation Toolkit. HIS Engage. <https://hisengage.scot/equipping-professionals/participation-toolkit/>
3. Life Changes Trust UK. (2016). Life Changes Trust Funding Evaluation Toolkit. Life Changes Trust Evaluation Toolkit. <http://www.lctevaluationtoolkit.com/participatory-evaluation>
4. Murthy, R. K. (2015). Toolkit on Gender-sensitive Participatory Evaluation Methods | Participatory Methods.
5. <https://www.participatorymethods.org/resource/toolkit-gender-sensitive-participatory-evaluation-methods>
6. Save the Children Norway. (2008). A Kit of Tools for Participatory Research and Evaluation with Children, Young People and Adults. BetterEvaluation. https://www.betterevaluation.org/en/resources/toolkit/a_kit_tools_participatory_research

16.00-18.00h. M4: Mentoring and working together

We are approaching the end of the school. Take advantage of this last mentoring session to reflect on the overall content of the sessions. You will put together all the lessons learned identifying what is more interesting and important for your group and shape the final presentation. Revise your interactions with other school participants and lecturers during the school. Identify doubts and issues you can solve in this session or how to approach them in the future. Make sure to strengthen your network of peers and analyse possibilities of future collaborations.

Day 9 – Thursday, September 23

13.30-15.30h. S5: Putting Citizen Social Science experiences together: YouCount, COESO, SoCis, ActEarly and CoAct

Katharina Buse, Project Advisor European Research Agency (REA)

Reidun Norvoll and Aina Landsverk Hagen, Oslo Metropolitan University

Alessia Smaniotto, OpenEdition

Claudia Göbel, Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg

Alexandra Albert, University College of London

Josep Perelló, Universitat de Barcelona

In this session you will get to know different Citizen Social Science projects at a glance. Coordinators and experts on each project will share their experiences in a mutual learning process. Your participation and other students' enquiries and views are expected to enrich this round table.

YouCount

The presentation is linked to the EU- SwafS project '**YouCount – Empowering youth and cocreating social innovation and policymaking through youth- focused citizen social science**', that will run from February 2021-January 2024. The overarching objective of the project is to generate new knowledge and innovations to increase the social inclusion of youth at risk of exclusion through co-creative youth citizen social science and to provide evidence of the actual outcomes of this. The project consists of 11 partners across Europe and will conduct a multiple case study in nine countries where young people (15- 29 years old) will participate as young citizen social scientists. In this presentation we will focus on how to plan for meaningful engagement with local youth throughout the various phases of a research process. The YouCount team in Norway will recruit and train a core group of 10-12 youth and young adults with the aim of gathering data on employment and social entrepreneurship in the city district of Gamle Oslo. In this district most of the youth have multicultural backgrounds, and a pressing challenge is to secure the first jobs in an area with

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high level of unemployment and recurring discrimination on the job market. How can we facilitate for inclusive and flexible spaces of engagement and peer-to-peer support, while simultaneously ensure rigidity in both data collection and analysis?

METHODOLOGIES SELECTED BY YOUCOUNT

The YouCount project will make use of a mixed-methods design: combining an overarching methodological design allowing for large scale and comparative cross-case analysis at the same time allowing for flexible approaches that fits the local case and targeted youth group. In Oslo, the YouCount team will build on previous experience of training youth in so-called 'youthnography', mixing traditional ethnographic elements with a positive psychology approach. The aim is to expand the repertoire of research tools available for methodological testing and experimentation, in alliance with the youth.

KEY RESOURCES FOR YOUCOUNT

Hecker, S., Haklay, M., Bowser, A., Makuch, Z., Vogel, J., & Bonn, A. (Eds.) *Citizen Science, Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy*. London: UCL Press.

Kieslinger, B., Schäfer, T., Heigl, F., Dörler, D., Richter, A., & Bonn, A. (2017). *The challenge of evaluation: An open framework for evaluating citizen science activities*.

<https://osf.io/preprints/socarxiv/enzc9>. Brossard, D., Lewenstein, B., & Bonney, R. (2005).

Scientific knowledge and attitude change: The impact of a citizen science project.

International Journal of Science Education, 27(9), 1099-1121

Irwin, A. (1995). *Citizen Science: A Study of People, Expertise, and Sustainable Development*. London: Routledge

Heiss, R., & Matthes, J. (2017). **Citizen science in the social sciences: a call for more evidence**. *GAIA-Ecological Perspectives for Science and Society*, 26(1), 22-26.

Richardons, L. (2013). Engaging the public in policy research: are community researchers the answer? *Politics and Governance*, 2(1), 32–44.

Ballard, H. L., Dixon, C. G. H., & Harris, E. M. (2017). Youth citizen science: examining the role of environmental science learning and agency for conservation. *Biological Conservation*, 208, 65–75. doi:10.1016/j.biocon.2016.05.024

Richardson, L. (2017). *Citizen social science and policy-making. Methods that matter: Social science and evidence-based policy-making*. Bristol, UK: The Policy Press

Kullenberg, C., & Kasperowski, D. (2016). What is citizen science? – A scientometric meta-analysis. (Report). *PLoS ONE*, 11(1), doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0147152

Hagen, A.L. (forthcoming november 2021) Egalitarian ideals, conflicting realities: Introducing a new model for thick youth participation in planning, in A.L., Hagen & B, Andersen (eds.) *Ung medvirkning. Kreativitet og konflikter i planlegging*. Ch.13. Oslo: Cappelen Damm Akademiske.

Thorstensen, E., Brattbakk, I. & Hagen, A.L. (2021). Images of Place, Secularity and Gentrification: On Urban Religious Belonging in an Inner City Neighbourhood in Oslo. *Secularism and Nonreligion*, 10: 3, pp. 1–16. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5334/snr.144>

Hagen, A.L. & Osuldsen, J. (forthcoming July 2021) Urban youth, narrative dialogues, and emotional imprints: How co-creating the ‘spotting’ methodology became a transformative journey into interdisciplinary collaboration in Stender, M., C. Bech-Danielsen & Hagen, A.L. (red.). *Architectural Anthropology – Exploring lived space*. Ch.8, pp.135-148. New York: Routledge.

Tolstad, I., Hagen, A.L. & Andersen, B. (2017) The amplifier effect: Youth co-creating urban spaces of belonging through art, architecture and anthropology, in S. Bastien & H. Holmarsdottir. *Youth as architects of change: global efforts to advance youth-driven innovation for social change* (eds.). pp. 215-242. Palgrave Macmillan.

The project has just started, the educational materials and toolkits developed in the project will thus come in a later stage.

SOCIS

Literature and guidelines for Citizen (Social) Science - C(S)S - focus on *participation* of non-professional researchers in science. The address how to motivate participants, how to ensure scientific standards, what technologies and methodologies can help, etc. But this participation doesn't happen in a vacuum. However, we don't know and talk much about the *contexts* that are needed to make C(S)S activities work. This is what we have analysed as part of a two-year study on participatory research in the fields of humanities and social sciences (our definition of CSS) in Germany. We found that CSS activities very often happen in diverse projects of various groups of academic and non-academic people and organisations. These consortia influence how participation works. I will introduce the notion of '*cooperation capacity*' to work further with these observations, highlight various aspects important for cooperation capacity and give examples from CSS projects. This shift in attention - from the participation of individuals to cooperation on a collective level - brings to sight additional actors and activities that are mostly not, or only marginally, considered. They are important for making C(S)S successful in terms of impact and meaningful for those involved.

KEY RESOURCES FROM SOCIS

Working group on Empowerment, Inclusiveness & Equity in Citizen Science and Community-based Research jointly hosted by ECSA and LKN - community of practice with monthly meetings, input talks, active mailing list, joint activities: <https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/working-groups/empowerment-inclusiveness-equity/>

Paper elaborating the concept of 'cooperation capacity' based on our data:

Göbel, Claudia; Mauermeister, Sylvi; Henke, Justus. (under review). Citizen Social Science in Germany - cooperation beyond invited and uninvited participation

Graphic we've created on terminology and invisible actors in C(S)S:

Göbel, Claudia, Hippler, Susann, & Kiessling, Tim. (2021, June 25). What to call people involved in citizen science projects? - extended version. Zenodo.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5031990>

These (mostly German) **SoCiS resources** could also be useful for others:

Open Educational Resource with basics on CSS (German)

Guidelines on CSS for practitioners and decision-makers (German)

SoCiS Policy Paper (English)

All are accessible here: <https://www.hof.uni-halle.de/projekte/socis/>

COESO

COESO is a double-layer research project. It provides a framework for field research through ten collaborative projects (the pilots), from different SSH disciplines (history, philosophy, political science, sociology and anthropology) and involving artists, journalists, associative members, local authorities. And it studies these collaborations in order to develop a "collaboratory", a common digital framework allowing the different stakeholders to co-create new knowledge and solutions and disseminate them to society. The pilot level focuses on participatory approaches: e.g. small scale and high intensity collaborations, since the problem formulation to the common analysis. The "meta-level", studying the collaborations, will develop the collaboratory framework through a UX co-design approach, and develop a "cooperation analytics" system, in support of stakeholders' reflective feedback on their participatory experiences.

METHODOLOGIES SELECTED BY COESO

Participatory approaches involving small scale and high intensity collaborations face specific challenges: find the common problem/issue, adjusting methodologies (epistemic cultures), sharing data (sensitive or not), access to the literature/informations, differentiated outputs but also: find people to work with (need for: aligned vocabularies, links through communities, recover examples of platforms dedicated to participatory research in the SSH, ...) plan synchronous activities and manage asynchronous activities (e.g. find and access to common spaces/places for regular alignment, time to share and discuss, ...) Find the right balance between partners' symmetry/asymmetry (on the researchers side) understand and acknowledge the knowledge production outside the academic world understand and acknowledge the differentiated channels for knowledge sharing.

COESO project, by building a sustainable framework to support participatory research in the SSH through a co-design approach, by providing a comprehensive framework to assess participatory practices, and encouraging knowledge sharing through joint blogging activities, will provide relevant tools and resources to tackle the participatory research challenges.

KEY RESOURCES FROM COESO

Hypotheses.org blogging platform: hypotheses.org

COESO proof of concept (participatory researchers involving SSH researchers and journalists (in French) <https://places.hypotheses.org/>

ACTEARLY

ActEarly focuses on early life interventions to improve the health and opportunities of children living in two contrasting areas with high levels of child poverty: Bradford, West Yorkshire and Tower Hamlets, London. ActEarly aims to create City Collaboratory testbeds to support the identification, implementation and evaluation of upstream interventions within a whole system city setting. In this way ActEarly moves away from the ‘biomedical model’ of policy in health research, to consider the cumulative effect of multiple system-wide interventions in the prevention of physical and mental ill-health. Community empowerment is at the heart of our ActEarly ‘City Collaboratory’ approach and ActEarly is committed to genuine co-production with users to achieve acceptable, feasible, evaluable, replicable, and sustainable systems interventions with real impact. This approach is informed by learning from the successful work over 10 years in Bradford. This is a presentation of our co-production and citizen science strategy for the ActEarly consortium. The aim is to provide clear guidance to the consortium on how to implement co-production and citizen science activities effectively. These will be completed in July 2021, with a final workshop in September 2021. Through developing this strategy, we aim to build capacity for and support the wider ActEarly team in the design, conduct and dissemination of co-production and citizen science activities, and to lead/support innovation in co-production and citizen science methodologies to optimise ActEarly interventions and further methodological research.

METHODOLOGY SELECTED:

Our Co-production and Citizen Science theme group aims to lead and support high quality and robust co-production and citizen science across the ActEarly consortium. Over the course of the ActEarly programme we hope to answer the following question: *How can a broad range of co-production and citizen science methodologies support the effective delivery of ActEarly activities to achieve acceptable, feasible, evaluable, and sustainable systems interventions?* To co-produce our strategy we have used an Appreciative Inquiry model (AI), which focuses on strengths and resources within communities. As part of our development work, we are delivering workshops with key community groups and interviews with stakeholders.

RESOURCES:

1. ActEarly Website: <https://actearly.org.uk/>
2. Forthcoming co-production and citizen science strategy including list of principles for CP/CS
ECSA Working Group on CS 4Health: <https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/working-groups/citizen-science-for-health/>
3. Bromley by Bow Centre Community Engagement and citizen science:
<https://www.bbbc.org.uk/insights/research-and-evaluation/research-and-evaluation-bromley-by-bow-community-engagement-and-citizen-science/>
4. Bromley by Bow Centre Family Playrooms: <https://www.bbbc.org.uk/family-playrooms/>
5. Coproduction Collective: <https://www.coproductioncollective.co.uk/>

References

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11. Burawoy M (2005) For a public sociology: 2004 Presidential Address to the American Sociological Association. Am Soc Rev 70(1):4–28
12. Büscher M, Urry J (2009) Mobile methods and the empirical. EU J Soc Theory 12(1):99–116
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15. Jasanoff S (eds) (2004) States of knowledge: the co-production of science and the social order. Routledge, London
16. Lewis, J (2012) How to implement free, prior informed consent (FPIC). Participatory Learning and Action 65: Biodiversity and culture: exploring community protocols, rights and consent. <https://www.iied.org/pla-65-biodiversity-culture-exploring-community-protocols-rights-consent>
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18. Mattern S (2016) Public in/formation. Places J. <https://doi.org/10.22269/161115>
19. Pollen A (2013) Research methodology in mass observation past and present: ‘Scientifically, about as valuable as a chimpanzee’s tea party at the zoo’? Hist Workshop J 75(1):213–235
20. Purdam K (2014) Citizen social science and citizen data? Methodological and ethical challenges for social research. Curr Soc 62(3):374–392
21. Rashid, R., et al. Taking a deep breath: a qualitative study exploring acceptability and perceived unintended consequences of charging clean air zones and air quality

- improvement initiatives amongst low-income, multi-ethnic communities in Bradford, UK. BMC Public Health 21, 1305 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-11337-z>
22. Tauginienė L, Butkevičienė E, Vohland K et al. (2020) Citizen science in the social sciences and humanities: the power of Interdisciplinarity. Palgrave Commun 6:89
23. Wright J, Hayward A, West J, Pickett K, McEachan R, Mon-Williams M, et al. **ActEarly: a City Collaboratory approach to early promotion of good health and wellbeing** [version 1; peer review: 1 approved]. Wellcome Open Research. 2019;4(156).

16.00-18.00h. STUDENTS PRESENTATIONS!

We will be closing the school with the students' reflections on Citizen Social Science applied to their different research topics and backgrounds. Your work during the mentoring sessions will be presented by your group. Together you can decide the spokesperson/s and the tools and way to present. Duration for each presentation: 15 min (present + feedback), depending on the final number of groups. There will be a final and collective discussion on the whole school experience. We hope that this will just one first step to start working to enhancement of social dimensions in Citizen Science!

3.11 Lecturers

AINA LANDSVERK HAGEN

Senior researcher

Project Coordinator/Leader for the Norwegian case of YouCount

Work Research Institute

Oslo Metropolitan University

Ph.D. in social anthropology from the University of Oslo on collaborative creativity among architects in Oslo and New York. She researches topics like urban development, youth participation, freedom of speech, innovation, and idea development, and continually develops methods and tools within citizen social science projects involving youth, local stakeholders, and transdisciplinary researchers.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

S5: Putting Citizen Social Science experiences together: YouCount, COESO, SoCis, ActEarly and CoAct. Day 9 – Thursday, September 23rd, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

ALESSIA SMANIOTTO

OpenEdition - International Development Service

Citizen Science Officer for the OPERAS community

Project Manager COESO

Trained in philosophy, journalism and sociology between Italy and France, Alessia Smaniotto holds a PhD in Philosophy from the École des Hautes Études en Sciences Sociales (EHESS). Before reinvesting her skills in research and research communication, she worked as a journalist in public and private media in Italy and she was a trainer at the Master of Journalism in Turin. She develops citizen science projects and services for the OPERAS community and works for OpenEdition Center, a French research center developing a comprehensive digital publishing infrastructure at the service of scholarly communication in the Humanities and Social Sciences (www.openedition.org). She currently manages the European project COESO - Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues, aiming to develop and sustain citizen science research in the social sciences and humanities.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

S5: Putting Citizen Social Science experiences together: YouCount, COESO, SoCis, ActEarly and CoAct. Day 9 – Thursday, September 23rd, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

ALEXANDRA ALBERT

Senior Research Fellow

ActEarly

Extreme Citizen Science Research Group

Geography Department

University College London, UK

Alexandra Albert is a post-doctoral researcher on ActEarly UKPRP, examining citizen science and co-production in early life interventions to improve health opportunities for children in the UK. Her PhD research was a critical investigation of how citizen social science works in practice. Her research interests include citizen social science, co-production, citizen science, public sociology, participatory inventive methods.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

S5: Putting Citizen Social Science experiences together: YouCount, COESO, SoCis, ActEarly and CoAct. Day 9 – Thursday, September 23rd, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

AMANDA MASHA CAMINALS

Co-director and curator

Mutant Institute of Environmental Narratives
(IMNA)

Matadero Madrid

Photo: Matadero / Lukasz Michalak

Amanda Masha Caminals is co-director and curator of the Mutant Institute of Environmental Narratives (IMNA), the artistic laboratory for climate action of Matadero Madrid. She is also Advisor to the European Commission S+T+ARTS Prize. Previous to that, she directed the CITY STATION of the Centre for Contemporary Culture of Barcelona and founded the organization Translocalia, a network of artists, curators and designers to plan for the future through art. She has worked in institutions including the Institute of International Visual Arts in London and Casa Triângulo in São Paulo. She holds a BA in Humanities from Pompeu Fabra University in Barcelona, a Degree in History of Art from the University of Barcelona and an MA Hons in Curating Contemporary Art from the Royal College of Art in London.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

S3: Public and collective experiments on social issues: public space, social behaviour and collaboration in cultural contexts. Day 6 – Friday, September 17th, 2021 – 16.00-18.00 h

ANNA CIGARINI

PhD candidate

OpenSystems, Universitat de Barcelona

Dimmons, Universitat Oberta de Catalunya

Anna Cigarini is member of OpenSystems since 2017 and phd candidate at Universitat Oberta de Catalunya. She is interested in participatory research methods and citizen science, commons governance systems, their intersections with digital technologies and their social effects. Her research focuses on the overlaps between citizen science and commons-based peer production models, and on the role and potential of commons-oriented citizen science practices for communities' organization and activism.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

W1: CoAct for Mental Health: sharing first-hand experiences and cocreating a chatbot for a citizen social science research. Day 2 – Tuesday, September 14th, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

CHRIS SALTER

Artist

Professor for Design + Computation Arts

Concordia University

Co-Director of the Hexagram network Researcher

Chris Salter is an artist, Professor for Design + Computation Arts at Concordia University in Montreal and Co-Director of the Hexagram network. He studied philosophy, economics, theatre and computer music at Emory and Stanford Universities. His artistic work has been seen internationally at the Venice Architecture Biennale, Barbican Centre, Berliner Festspiele, Wiener Festwochen, ZKM, Musée d'art Contemporain, among many others. He is the author of *Entangled: Technology and the Transformation of Performance* and *Alien Agency: Experimental Encounters with Art in the Making* (both MIT Press). His new book *Sensing Machines* will be published by MIT Press in March 2022.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

S3: Public and collective experiments on social issues: public space, social behaviour and collaboration in cultural contexts. Day 6 – Friday, September 17th, 2021 – 16.00-18.00 h

CLAUDIA GÖBEL

Researcher

Institute for Higher Education Research (HoF)

University Halle-Wittenberg

Claudia Göbel is a social scientist and practitioner in the field of open participatory research. She works on open organisations, research policy and equity in Citizen (Social) Sciences. Her background is in science and technology studies. She is co-chairing the working group on “Empowerment, Inclusiveness and Equity” at the European Citizen Science Association and the Living Knowledge Network.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

S5: Putting Citizen Social Science experiences together: YouCount, COESO, SoCis, ActEarly and CoAct. Day 9 – Thursday, September 23th, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

DAVID SCHELLER

Postdoctoral researcher

Department of Social and Educational Science

Potsdam University of Applied Sciences (FHP)

David Scheller is a sociologist and an urban researcher working as a postdoctoral researcher for CoAct at the Department of Social and Educational Science at the Potsdam University of Applied Sciences. He is responsible for exploring the foundations of participatory methodologies in Citizen Social Science (CSS) and the compilation of a CSS toolkit. His research focuses mainly on urban social movements, collective housing, sustainable urban development, social inequality, community building, commoning and democratization from a comparative and intersectional perspective. For more information check this [website](#).

YOU WILL MEET HIM AT:

S0: Citizen Social Science: Enhancing social dimensions in Citizen Science. Day 1 – Monday, September 13th, 2021 – 14.00-16.00 h

W4: The research forum as a methodological foundation for communication and participation in co-creational CSS. Day 5 – Friday, September 17th, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

EVELIN HEIDEL

Digital rights activist

Community strategist

Climate Change Wikiproject

Evelin Heidel (aka Scann) is a digital rights activist and community strategist, who has worked at the intersection of digital rights, digital heritage and copyright in Latin America for over ten years. She holds a BA in Literature (University of Buenos Aires, Argentina) and is currently enrolled in a Masters Program in Law & Economics of Climate Change at the Latin American Faculty of Social Sciences (FLACSO). She is the founder of the Wikiproject Climate Change in Spanish Wikipedia and is collaborating with Shannon on the Open Climate initiative.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

S2: Social Dimensions in Citizen Science: Leveraging the knowledge commons. Day 4 – Thursday, September 16th, 2021 – 16.00-18.00 h

FRANZISKA PETER

Postdoctoral researcher

OpenSystems group member

Universitat de Barcelona

Franziska Peter started her postdoc on digital tools for participatory research in 2020 in the EU Horizon 2020 CoAct project. Her doctoral thesis in theoretical physics was dedicated to emergent phenomena in finite size nonlinear systems. She currently develops and co-creates the Telegram chatbot “CoActuem per la Salut Mental” that allows the team of (co-)researchers to interact with thousands of participants and gather their experiences and reactions with and on mental health situations. She will co-investigate the collected data with statistical physics, network science, and machine learning methods.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

W1: CoAct for Mental Health: sharing first-hand experiences and cocreating a chatbot for a citizen social science research. Day 2 – Tuesday, September 14th, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

GUILLERMINA ACTIS

Researcher

Argentina Research Council

Research Center for Transformation

Universidad Nacional de San Martin

Guillermina Actis, Political Scientist (University of Buenos Aires, Argentina); Master in Public Policy (University Torcuato Di Tella, Argentina). She completed postgraduate studies in Science, Technology and Society (National University of Quilmes, Argentina). She is a Phd Student in a Doctorate in Science and Technology, (National University of Quilmes, Argentina) working on citizen science for policy making. Since 2020, she is a member in CoAct R&I Action team on Environmental Justice at the Matanza -Riachuelo river basin in Buenos Aires. (CENIT, UNSAM).

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

W2: Digital Participation in vulnerable contexts during Covid times. Day 3 – Wednesday, September 15th, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

IGNASI LABASTIDA

Open Science Rector's delegate

Head of Research Support Unit

Universitat de Barcelona

Ignasi Labastida is the Rector's Delegate for Open Science at the University of Barcelona and the Head of the Research Support Unit at the Library. Currently he is chairing the LERU Information and Open Access Policy Group and the Board of SPARC Europe.

YOU WILL MEET HIM AT:

W5: Open Science in Citizen Social Science projects: general framework and practical guidelines. Day 6 – Monday, September 20th, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

IRENE AGRIVINA

Founder

HONF

Open systems advocate, technologist, artist and educator Irene Agrivina is a graduate of the Graphic Design faculty at the Indonesia Institute of Art (ISI), Yogyakarta, and continuing her study at Culture and Religion Master Program at Sanata Dharma University in Yogyakarta. She is one of the founding members and current directors of HONF, the Yogyakarta based new media and technology laboratory. Created in 1998 as a place of open expression, art and cultural technologies in the wake of the Indonesian "revolution", HONF aka the 'House of Natural Fiber' was born out of the social and political turmoil against the Suharto regime, its nepotism and governmental corruption. Agrivina runs HONF's 'Education Focus Programme' (EFP) which focuses on the application and practical use in daily life of collaborative, cross-disciplinary and technological actions responding to social, cultural and environmental challenges. In response to the needs of societies in development and transition, HONF and EFP apply open, collaborative and sustainable actions that systematically expand or convert accessible technologies to be used as multifunctional tools and methodologies.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

S4: Knowledge Production with Makers: Situatedness, Infrastructuring and Critical Practice. Day 6 – Monday, September 20th, 2021 – 16.00-18.00 h

ISABELLE BONHOURE

Researcher

OpenSystems group member

Universitat de Barcelona

Isabelle Bonhoure joined OpenSystems grup from Universitat de Barcelona in 2013. She has a PhD in materials science but a diverse research experience including environmental, public health in the global south and citizen science related studies. She is particularly interested in citizen social science implications in terms of bottom-up co-creation processes and involvement of citizens in a vulnerable situation.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

S0: Citizen Social Science: Enhancing social dimensions in Citizen Science. Day 1 – Monday, September 13th, 2021 – 14.00-16.00 h

W1: CoAct for Mental Health: sharing first-hand experiences and cocreating a chatbot for a citizen social science research. Day 2 – Tuesday, September 14th, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

GEORGINA NICOLAU

Founder

Procomum Institute

Georgia Nicolau is a creative professional, researcher, trained facilitator and consultant in the areas of social organizations, social justice, culture and arts and social innovation. In 2016, she co-founded Procomum Institute, a commons-based organization where she is currently director of programs and partnerships and institutional development. She is the co-author on the following books: “Bottom Up” on culture and digital innovation; “Solidary economy of culture and cultural citizenship: challenges and horizons”; “Digital culture, Internet and political appropriations: experiences, challenges and horizons”; and is one of the personalities portrayed in the book Generation Share: The Change-Makers Building the Sharing Economy. In 2020 she became a Fellow at the Atlantic Fellows for Social and Economic Equity programme at the London School of Economics and Political Science (LSE).

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

S4: Knowledge Production with Makers: Situatedness, Infrastructuring and Critical Practice. Day 6 – Monday, September 20th, 2021 – 16.00-18.00 h

JOSEP PERELLÓ

Full professor
OpenSystems group
Institute of Complex Systems
Universitat de Barcelona

Josep Perelló is full professor in the Universitat of Barcelona. In 2013, he founded the OpenSystems research group to run transdisciplinary scientific research with citizens' participation and artistic practices. Since then, he has conducted more than 20 public experiments (more than 7,000 participants) in collaboration with artists, designers, museums, cultural festivals and cultural centers. Experiments are mostly focused on human behavior in urban contexts within the broad label of Citizen Social Science. He currently coordinates the EU Horizon 2020 CoAct project.

YOU WILL MEET HIM AT:

S0: Citizen Social Science: Enhancing social dimensions in Citizen Science. Day 1 – Monday, September 13th, 2021 – 14.00-16.00 h

S3: Public and collective experiments on social issues: public space, social behaviour and collaboration in cultural contexts. Day 6 – Friday, September 17th, 2021 – 16.00-18.00 h

S5: Putting Citizen Social Science experiences together: YouCount, COESO, SoCis, ActEarly and CoAct. Day 9 – Thursday, September 23rd, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

JUAN FREIRE

Vice-chancellor

Innovation and Transformation

Universidad Tecmilenio

PhD in Environmental Biology, I developed a university career in Spain from 1990 to 2010. With this background in sustainability and environmental sciences my interests have evolved towards business management, digital culture, innovation, and education. I have co-founded 10 companies and startups.

Vice-Chancellor of Innovation and Transformation of Tecmilenio. Previously, Leader of the Strategic Initiative for Learning Platforms and Digital Acceleration, Academic and International Dean of the Business School and Visiting Professor of the School of Humanities and Education (2016) of the of the Tecnológico de Monterrey.

YOU WILL MEET HIM AT:

S1: Citizen labs for citizen innovation: opportunities and challenges. Day 2 – Tuesday, September 14th, 2021 – 16.00-18.00 h

KATJA MAYER

Senior researcher

Centre for Social Innovation (ZSI)

And University of Vienna

Katja Mayer is a sociologist at the University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies. Her research examines the interactions between social science methods and their public spheres, focusing on the cultural, ethical and socio-technical challenges at the interface of computer science, social sciences and society. In addition, she is Senior Scientist at the Center for Social Innovation in Vienna and as such involved in the CoAct project.

<https://homepage.univie.ac.at/katja.mayer>

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

W5: Open Science in Citizen Social Science projects: general framework and practical guidelines. Day 6 – Monday, September 20th, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

W7: Participatory Evaluation in Citizen Social Science. Day 8 – Wednesday, September 22nd, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

LETICIA CASTRO

Researcher

Argentina Research Council

Research Center for Transformation

Universidad Nacional de San Martin

Leticia Castro, Sociologist (Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina). Master in Research in Education, Cultural Diversity and Community Development (Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Spain). She completed postgraduate studies in Urban Social Policy (Universidad Nacional de Tres de Febrero, Argentina). She is Phd Student in a Doctorate in Urban Studies (Universidad de General Sarmiento, Argentina). Since 2021, she is a member in CoAct R&I Action team on Environmental Justice at the Matanza -Riachuelo river basin in Buenos Aires. (CENIT, UNSAM).

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

W2: Digital Participation in vulnerable contexts during Covid times. Day 3 – Wednesday, September 15th, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

MALENA VALVERDE

Researcher

Argentina Research Council

Research Center for Transformation

Universidad Nacional de San Martin

Malena Valverde is a graduate student at Latin American Literature program (UNSAM). She coordinates the extension program “Memorias Recientes” at Universidad de Buenos Aires. Since 2020, she is a member in CoAct R&I Action team on Environmental Justice at the Matanza -Riachuelo river basin in Buenos Aires-(CENIT, UNSAM).

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

W2: Digital Participation in vulnerable contexts during Covid times. Day 3 – Wednesday, September 15th, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

MARCOS GARCÍA

Citizen labs advisor
Distributed Citizen Laboratories
Former director and cofounder
Medialab Prado

Marcos García works in the field of citizen laboratories. Between 2003 and 2021 he worked at Medialab Prado. Between 2004 and 2006 he was responsible for the educational and mediation program of MediaLabMadrid together with Laura Fernández, where they promoted the *Interactivos?* project, a collaborative prototyping workshop format that served as the basis for the development of Medialab Prado and its citizen laboratory methodology. Between 2007 and 2014 he was responsible for the cultural program of Medialab Prado together with Laura Fernández, and between 2014 and 2021 its director.

In 2020 he started the project *Distributed Citizen Laboratories. Citizen innovation in libraries and other cultural institutions*, an initiative of the Ministry of Culture and Medialab Prado to promote the creation of citizen laboratories and cooperation between them, during the Covid-19 crisis. He currently advises different organizations on the start-up of citizen laboratories.

YOU WILL MEET HIM AT:

W2: Digital Participation in vulnerable contexts during Covid times. Day 3 – Wednesday, September 15th, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

NATALIA SANTOLARIA

Data journalist

Domestic Data Streamers

Data journalist at Domestic Data Streamers

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

W6: Play with Data. Day 7 – Tuesday, September 21st, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

PAU GARCIA

Catalyst

Domestic Data Streamers

Pau's focus of work is based on the areas of new media and data languages, leading the creative studio Domestic Data Streamers working in experimental research, communication and design projects for cultural institutions and organizations such as the California Academy of Sciences, TED, United Nations or Spotify. His second passion is in education where he invests his time in academic work as director of the Master in Data and Design at the Elisava School of Design and Engineering in Barcelona and as guest professor at Politecnico di Milano.

YOU WILL MEET HIM AT:

W6: Play with Data. Day 7 – Tuesday, September 21st, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

PACO GONZÁLEZ

Architect

Universitat Oberta de Catalunya

Paco González is an Architect (EQF-EHEA 7) with a career focused on new practices in architecture and the urban design fields. Now he is working on participatory design projects and developing the thesis project 'Civic labs. Urban experimentation and participatory cities' at TURBA research group IN3 of Universitat Oberta de Catalunya.

YOU WILL MEET HIM AT:

S1: Citizen labs for citizen innovation: opportunities and challenges. Day 2 – Tuesday, September 14th, 2021 – 16.00-18.00 h

PIA MARCHEGIANI

PhD Candidate

Latin American Faculty of Social Sciences (FLACSO)

Environmental Policy Director

Fundación Ambiente y Recursos Naturales (FARN)

Pía Marchegiani has a Law Degree from the University of Buenos Aires and a Master in Social Sciences, Global Studies Programme, jointly granted by the University of Freiburg, Germany and the University of Kwazulu-Natal, South Africa; Pía is a Phd candidate at the Latin American Faculty of Social Sciences (FLACSO-Argentina) researching on social and environmental impacts of lithium extraction in South America, She is also the Environmental Policy Director at Fundación Ambiente y Recursos Naturales (FARN) in which she works to enforce the rights of communities in different environmental issues and conflicts; she lectures at Flacso-Argentina and at the Environmental Law Legal Clinic, which is jointly conducted by FARN and the Faculty of Law of the University of Buenos Aires.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

S2: Social Dimensions in Citizen Science: Leveraging the knowledge commons. Day 4 – Thursday, September 16th, 2021 – 16.00-18.00 h

RAFFAELE IPPOLITO

PhD Candidate

University of Oxford

Raffaele Ippolito is a PhD candidate at School of Geography and the Environment, University of Oxford. His ethnographic research explores the experiences of industrial pollution and illness in fenceline communities in Italy and Taiwan, with a focus on the slow dimension of toxic exposure in the everyday life of residents. Raffaele is interested in studying the nexus between structural and epistemic violence and in the translation of grassroots epistemologies into environmental policy. Being originally from Taranto, he is also an active member of Giustizia per Taranto, an organisation pursuing environmental justice in the city home to Europe's largest steel factory.

YOU WILL MEET HIM AT:

S2: Social Dimensions in Citizen Science: Leveraging the knowledge commons. Day 4 –
Thursday, September 16th, 2021 – 16.00-18.00 h

REGINA SIPPOS

Research Associate

PhD Candidate Innovation

Technical University of Berlin

Institute of Vocational Education and Work Studies

Regina Sipos focuses communities in critical making, hacker culture, grassroots innovation, appropriate technologies and open source tech. She has more than a decade of experience working with grassroots: as the manager of the United Nations' first platform for social entrepreneurs working with technology, the founder of Social-Digital Innovation, executive board member of GIG and many more roles as researcher, public speaker, consultant and social innovator.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

S4: Knowledge Production with Makers: Situatedness, Infrastructuring and Critical Practice. Day 6 – Monday, September 20th, 2021 – 16.00-18.00 h

REIDUN NORVOLL

Research Professor
Project Coordinator YouCount
Work Research Institute
Oslo Metropolitan University

Reidun Norvoll, Ph.D. in sociology from the University of Oslo. Her research topics span across many topics. She has experience with health and mental health research and have worked with user and citizen involved or led research in many social contexts including health services and community settings. The interest in citizen social science is a continuation of her background in participatory (action) research.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

S5: Putting Citizen Social Science experiences together: YouCount, COESO, SoCis, ActEarly and CoAct. Day 9 – Thursday, September 23rd, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

SHANNON DOSEMAGEN

Fellow

Shuttleworth Foundation

Director

Open Environmental Data Project

Shannon Dosemagen is Director of the Open Environmental Data Project, focused on creating stronger systems for how we share, contribute and access open data and information. She previously served for a decade as Executive Director of Public Lab, a community that uses open technology, data and science to support communities in addressing environmental pollution. She previously Chaired the (U.S.) National Advisory Council on Environmental Policy and Technology (NACEPT) and the Citizen Science Association and currently sits on the board of directors for a wide range of organizations including the (U.S.) National Parks Conservation Association, Code for Science and Society, and the Gathering for Open Science Hardware.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

S2: Social Dimensions in Citizen Science: Leveraging the knowledge commons. Day 4 – Thursday, September 16th, 2021 – 16.00-18.00 h

SAAD CHINOY

Founder
SpudnikLab
Volunteer
EngineeringGood

Saad is a professional geek with a passion for technology and OpenSource methodology. Co founder of Singapore based Frugal Innovation startup, SpudnikLab, that works to address the #digitalDivide through digital skills education and effective use of low-cost technologies.

Aside from the professional context, Saad serves as a volunteer with EngineeringGood, a Non-profit Charity that supports the needs of persons with disabilities where he initiated SalvageGarden, the assistive technology Makerspace that engages a community of makers, engineers, care givers, persons with disabilities, and care professionals towards the research and development of Assistive Tech devices and low-cost solutions. The SalvageGarden Makerspace has recently initiated efforts towards environmental sustainability awareness by repurposing or recycling leftover e-waste parts from laptops donated to EngineeringGoods "Computers Against Covid" Campaign. Saad Also serves on the advisory boards of the Global Innovation Gathering, and r0g agency for open culture and critical transformation. Saad is a self-confessed maker and coffee epicure.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

S4: Knowledge Production with Makers: Situatedness, Infrastructuring and Critical Practice. Day 6 – Monday, September 20th, 2021 – 16.00-18.00 h

STEFAN THOMAS

Professor

Department of Social and Educational Science

Potsdam University of Applied Sciences (FHP)

Stefan Thomas is a professor of empirical social research and social work at the Department of Social and Educational Science at the University of Applied Sciences Potsdam since 2012. His academic work has a strong record in participatory research methodology, Citizen Social Science and mixed method approaches with respect to both conducting research and contributing to the debate on research methods. With an applied research approach and a transdisciplinary orientation, he aims to examine and develop innovative solutions for social problems.

YOU WILL MEET HIM AT:

W4: The research forum as a methodological foundation for communication and participation in co-creational CSS. Day 5 – Friday, September 17th, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

STEFANIE SCHUERZ

Research Associate

Centre for Social Innovation

University of Vienna

Stefanie Schuerz studied sociology and science and technology studies and currently works as a researcher at the Centre for Social Innovation. Her work focuses on different dimensions of participatory practices, and specifically on their capacity to enable more relevant research and innovation as well as social transformation.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

W7: Participatory Evaluation in Citizen Social Science. Day 8 – Wednesday, September 22nd, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

TERESA WINTERSTELLER

Junior researcher

Department of Education

University of Vienna

Teresa Wintersteller is a social- and cultural anthropologist and social worker. She is an expert in participatory action research with children and youth and focuses on the development of qualitative research methods for collaborative research practices. She is an experienced trainer in political education with young people and aims to combine approaches of non-formal education and scientific research. Her work is oriented towards social equality and empowerment and dedicated to questions of power and marginalization. Currently she is a leading project member of the CoAct team of the University of Vienna working on the topic of youth employment.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

W3: Methods Development for Participatory Social Research with Young People. Day 4 –
Thursday, September 16th, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

VALERIA ARZA

Researcher

Argentina Research Council

Research Center for Transformation

Universidad Nacional San Martin

Valeria Arza, Phd SPRU-University of Sussex. She is a researcher at CONICET (Argentinean Research Council) with a workplace at CENIT (Research Center for Transformation), National University of San Martin (UNSAM). She has over 10 years of experience as project leader in the area of science, technology and innovation policies studies. She has been actively contributing to the global research agenda on open science since 2015. She currently coordinates the R&I action on Environmental Justice from CoAct.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

W2: Digital Participation in vulnerable contexts during Covid times. Day 3 – Wednesday, September 15th, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

VERONIKA WÖHRER

Professor

Department of Education

University of Vienna

Veronika Wöhrer is sociologist and professor for 'Inequality and Education' at the Department of Education at the University of Vienna (Austria). She has directed several participatory research projects with children and young people and published on this topic. Her research interests are sociology of education, intersectionality, gender studies, qualitative research and participatory action research.

YOU WILL MEET HER AT:

W3: Methods Development for Participatory Social Research with Young People. Day 4 – Thursday, September 16th, 2021 – 13.30-15.30 h

4. Concluding remarks

The present deliverable includes the open training materials that have been used for the CoAct Citizen Social Science School. The school has no precedent in the context of Citizen Social Science and there exists very few experiences in the context of citizen science. The school has already identified a strong interest from early-career researchers to the methods, ideas, projects, experiences that contribute to the enhancement of the social dimension of citizen science. Participants to the school highly valued the effort of compiling extensively and systematically the information provided by the lecturers. They acknowledge this effort to provide a wide variety of resources to further explore Citizen Social Science. It is however also true that the online format has limited the attention capacity of participants which asked for more discussion and joint reflection. In order to respond to this need, a periodic meeting is planned to be organised with school participants.

COVID has forced us to move to an online format. The online format has allowed to reach a wider and a more diverse profile of participants and has thus promoted a transdisciplinary perspective when looking at Citizen Social Science participatory research. The online format has also facilitated the production of contents which are now left open in the CoAct project webpage. ZSI did run a short survey when the school finished. Mild criticism was only voiced about time management: “There was enough time for reflection and experience exchange with others”. This question reached the lowest mean with an average rating of 5,7, which demonstrates the overall very high satisfaction of participants with the Summer School in terms of goals, provided knowledge, room for questions and overall value of the event, among others (see Deliverable 7.2 for more details).

It is finally remarkable that the school participants received an official recognition from Universitat de Barcelona. Universitat de Barcelona has left open the possibility of repeating the school in the future, at least through the UB school of doctorate. The training materials created will certainly make more feasible this possibility which will surely contribute to the spread of citizen science in one of the most important universities in Spain.